

ELOQUENT SILENCE, JESUS AND SERVANT LEADERSHIP

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Abstract

This study combined eloquent silence and Jesus' Servant Leadership as a concept of leadership, which is a form of communication with theological relevance. This allows for human choice, introspection, and free-will decisions. The current world is a world of assertion, argument, competition, and survival of the fittest. This problem has tipped leadership against themselves; leadership against followers and followers against each other. The methodology was qualitative, mediated by theological analysis and selected secular case studies, such as Jesus, Job, Socrates, Holocaust victims, Mahatma Gandhi, and Nelson Mandela. The research design was based on a literature search and content analysis. These were instrumental to the elicitation of textual data, which were synthesized to generate themes and patterns for general discussions and implications. The study found that though quiet, silence is eloquent. It clarifies human intentions and is meaning making for doctrines, ethics, moral independence, integrity, and justice. In alignment with servant leadership, silent communication had no evidence of domination, manipulation, coercion, aggression, nor contention. By interpretation, eloquent silence was counter cultural. It went against every negative leadership practice. Consequently, if understood correctly, silence was an immensely powerful model of leadership, which should form the foundation of every leadership style. Overall, if the freewill choice of the followers is not engaged, assertiveness, self-imposition, and charisma are different from performance, effectiveness, and efficiency.

Keywords: Eloquent Silence, Jesus, Servant Leadership, Service.

Introduction

The purpose of this paper is to examine Jesus' choice of silence as a method of intentional communication and a unique aspect of His Servant Leadership. Unlike humanity, when Jesus remained silent or kept mute to a direct question or in a horrific situation, it does not mean that He was bereft of information, power, or knowledge of what to say or do. Instead, Jesus chose silence when falsely accused, when there are covetous power struggles and during clear injustice against His person. He used these as forms of leadership traits. Hence, Servant leadership is extraordinarily strong in eloquent silence. The leader is a servant to the followers. To this end, commitment is deepened and trust is established (Ramli & Desa, 2013) and development is realized (Srouf et al., 2024). Words are not spoken to allow others a reasonable time to think, decide and act without impairing their personality makeup and moral independence (Baldonado, 2019).

Silence means muteness, quiet, calmness, taciturnity, reticence, quiescence etc. However, used by Jesus, these words are used and understood differently. They applied for pedagogical reasons and to elicit different responses from the audience, through some non-verbal cues (López Gutiérrez & Arroyo Paniagua, 2024). Divine silent communication reveals that humanity is limited in knowledge and in how much it will ever know. It therefore requires dependence on God and not to second guess divine knowledge. Being limited, human beings do not have to know everything. Consequently, instead of seeking perfect knowledge, the humble thing for humanity is to live by faith in its limitations and weaknesses to derive meaning from the silence of Jesus.

Silence is eloquent. It is loud and sometimes even deafening. Many may struggle with listening to silence and understanding its meaning. This may be a derivative of modern leadership research and practice. This is to the extent that leadership progress and effectiveness are based on eloquence, visibility, and assertiveness. Silence is not charismatic. It is simply quiet, unassuming, and taciturn. Silent or verbal, Jesus was an engaging personality. He was always communicating meaningfully. Sometimes He asked questions, at other times He told a parable, or made a statement of fact. Yet very captivating are the moments He remained mute, as if He had nothing to say. The Gospels present Him both as quiet and expressive. His response to every situation was mediated by His perfect understanding of His audience and the better way to communicate to them (Kostrešević, 2021). These variations present theological and methodological principles that this study seeks to examine.

Jesus is a servant leader. He embodied it and lived it out in His ministry (Mark 10: 42; John 13: 1-17). Just like no one can claim to have manufactured water, literature identifies Him as a Servant Leader, and that name has stock, but this style of leadership was not founded by any researcher. Esera (2023) insists that the main aspect of Servant Leadership is service-oriented. The servant leader gives, gives, and gives again. Self is not asserted nor defended in the process of servant leadership. Domination, coercion, aggression, and contention are ignored (Song, 2024). Instead, the Servant leader leads to commitment for improved performance (Asamoah & Bigodza, 2024).

The methodology was qualitative, mediated by theological syntheses and selected secular case studies. The research design was based on a literature search and content analysis. These were instrumental to the elicitation of textual data, which were synthesized to generate themes and patterns for general discussions in the body of the paper.

The triangulation of Eloquent Silence, Jesus, and Servant Leadership address many questions. Such questions direct attention to the theology and meaning behind the Eloquent Silence approach of Jesus and its relationship to Servant leadership and silence as a communication method in a world of survival of the fittest. To address these issues, the remaining parts of the paper covers the theological bases for Eloquent Silence. Jesus and specific case studies of Eloquent Silence. Principles of Servant Leadership. Secular case studies of Eloquent Silence. Discussions on Jesus, Eloquent Silence, and Servant Leadership. Recommendations were made and conclusions drawn.

Theological Bases For Eloquent Silence

The Bible uses silence in diverse ways and for varied reasons. Silence is eloquent depending on how it is applied and who applies it. Jesus is the Master of communication in silence. He can use it to communicate in very eloquent ways. Whether to humanity, a situation or to a person, in a worship setting or at divine presence, silence has impactful effects in each of them (Kyei, 2023). In the presence of God, there is an apparent ordination for silence. Habakkuk 2:20 implies that the holy presence of God evokes silence; that is, His presence elicits silence. Hence, in all places of worship, there is an unspoken command of silence. In the understanding of Habakkuk, silence in the presence of God is a form of reverence, because He is infinite and great. (White, 2000). To further deepen this ambience, Zephaniah 1:7 simply instructs that everyone should “Be silent before the Lord GOD.” In obedience, Aaron held his peace before God’s judgment (Leviticus 10:3), on the death of his two children who offered strange fire before the Lord (Leviticus 10:1). The direct reason for silence in the presence of God is because of His divine glory. For example, when the Lamb of God, Jesus, opened the seventh seal, there was silence in heaven for about thirty minutes (Revelation 8:1), in the observance of His Majesty.

There is some sense in the adage that ‘empty barrels make the most noise.’ People who lack knowledge often speak first and loudly. It means that those who speak long and loudly lack restraint and control over themselves. Theologically, Proverbs 17:27,18 links silence with the substance of understanding, intelligence, and wisdom. Ardana and Surya (2019) agree that it takes wisdom to put silence to a useful end. Such people speak expensive words because they speak few and sparingly. Their speech is not out of want but out of need. This point is not a suggestion of speechless silence of the dumb, but the wisdom of the wise and the discerning, knowing when to be silent and when to speak (Ecclesiastes 3:7). So, whether one abounds or is abased, listening is better than speaking (James 1:19) and being in control of one’s tongue is evidence of tending towards maturity (James 3:2).

One typical example of when speaking eloquently in silence is during times of suffering. Job learnt this lesson in a very hard and personal way. Hence, in Job 13:5, he admonishes that the sufferer is wise if he or she keeps silent in the ordeal. This is instructive because, by complaining during suffering, the agony is doubled into the physical and the psychological. Human experience shows that one is talkative during suffering. Job showed this human undulation during his ordeal; thus, his counsel when he realized himself is significant. He promised to stop talking by covering his mouth with his hand and to restrain himself from further speeches (Job 40:4,5). Even in his laments, Jeremiah encourages silence as a form of hope (Lamentation 3:26-28), to which God will react (Psalms 39:9), even in the silent intercessions of the Holy Spirit (Romans 8: 26) and the unspeakable revelations of the Lord (2 Corinthians 12:4).

At the natural level, everybody will speak for and defend themselves. A kind of survival of the fittest, which is a means to the end of the self-destruction of the entire humanity. But God is sovereign and omnipotent. Faith and submission to His perfect produces an end of bliss in eternity. In this sense, silence is not weak (Isaiah 30: 15). It is a spiritual discipline that indicates trust, reverence, and faithful confidence in God (Psalm 4:4; Psalm 131:2; Matthew 6:6 and Colossians 3:16). One that is still and remains silent in a horrendous situation is waiting for the Lord to fight (Exodus 14:14; Psalms 62:1 and Hebrews 10:36). On the cross, at His highest ordeal, Jesus could have stepped down from the cross and fly away to heaven. Instead, while

remaining silent to His murderers, He commended His spirit into the hand of His Father (Luke 23:46). Hopefully, according to Kuang et al. (2015), His silence to their cruel act can create in them an attitude of reflection.

There are situations where spoken words will only meet with deaf ears. Though it may cause pain, that is when silence is most eloquent. In Mark 15, the chief priests, elders, and scribes have decided that Jesus must be crucified, so when in verse three they accused Him of many things, He kept silent. Again, in verse thirteen when the crowd shouted, 'crucify Him,' Jesus simply responded in silence to them. According to Psalm 38:13,14, silence is good when one is facing false accusation and, Jesus was fulfilling prophecy in that he was silent before His oppressors (Isaiah 53: 7; Matthew 26: 62,63 and 1 Peter 2:23). The fact is that to keep one's integrity intact, safeguard one's integrity and prove one's accusers eternally wrong, defense before false accusers is a waste of words. Silence and righteous quietude, even at the cost of shame, suffering and death, is more noble and impactful.

If He desires to, Jesus can speak humanity to a point of becoming deaf and dumb. He chooses silent communication as a form of restraint on His part, to allow human beings to think and choose freely. This allows one the time to reflect on the matter and make an intelligent decision. God spoke to Elijah in a still small voice, (1 Kings 19:11-13). David taught that in being silent, the believer will understand God and recognize His powers. Jesus communicated with His Father in silent prayers (Mark 1:35 and Luke 5:16). Jesus knew that in everything that happens on earth, God has the final say. Judgements may be unjust and manipulated here on earth; God will judge every case again. His will be fair and final. The rewards of such cases will not be earthly, but heavenly. Those who keep silent on certain wrongs, accusations, and partialities, but commit their safety in prayers, into the keeping of the Lord, will be vindicated at last. When true believers remain silent on earth, they are heavenly vocal. The wicked will not have a voice in the day of the Lord (Zephaniah 1:7). The sinners will be mute and in shame before the divine judgement of God (Habakkuk 2:20 and Revelation 8:1). The righteous though silent to many unfavorable situations on earth, are expectant of the final judgment of God, but those do not do the will of God will be in abhorrence of the Second Appearing of Jesus Christ.

The point had been made earlier that divine silence and human silence are not one and the same, neither do they produce the same effect. The silence of God is much more eloquent than the eloquence of humanity. Divine silence communicates to human beings, self-reflection, and retrospect (Masoga, 2024). It is evident of divine power, authority, and wisdom. This is because divine silence is not out of lack of knowledge. Divine silence allows the will of God to be done (Isaiah 53; Mathew 27:12-14; Mark 14:60,61; Luke 23:9 and John 19:9-11). During His trials and crucifixion, if Jesus had tried in any way to prove His innocence, His accusers would not have been able to defend themselves before Him. They would not have succeeded in giving Him into the hands of Pilate for crucifixion. The will of God would have been thwarted.

Jesus And Specific Case Studies Of Eloquent Silence

Jesus did not always respond to questions, nor did He react to every situation. When Jesus used silent communication, it does not mean that He did not understand the question or the problem. Rather, silence approach helped to clarify the matter and gave it depth (Ajayi, 2025). In some cases, the questions were answered later in another forum, when communication will be clear,

understood, and accepted (Ajayi, 2025). Otherwise, the problem was solved in another situation through the personal suffering and pain of Jesus. Whichever it is, silent communication was a method used by Him to unearth the motivations of human beings and thus allow them an uninterrupted opportunity to make a free decision of either obedience or disobedience (Yagil and Oren, 2021).

Jesus was with Caiaphas, the high priest. The stakes were matters of life or death. Jesus knew the decision He had made, to die for human sin. The council had concluded to crucify Jesus. Hence, the outcome of the situation was not a matter of questions and answers. It was not a situation of right or wrong. The two witnesses who came up were false. But they were hand-picked and properly schooled for illegality. In this case, silence was louder than words. It was pointless to speak words to men who have covenanted themselves to do evil. (Dhaqane, 2024). According to their confessions, Jesus blasphemed against the Jerusalem temple. "... This fellow (Jesus) said, I can destroy the temple of God, and to build it in three days." [Matthew 26:61 & Mark 14:58]. Jesus kept silent, probably because He knew that He referred not to the physical temple, but to His body temple, pointing to His death and resurrection [John 2:21,22]. The Jews did not understand when He first made the statement about the destruction of the temple in John 2:20. Consequently, the people needed to go through the process of Jesus' death and resurrection to understand the words of Jesus. This requirement necessitated communication in silence [Matthew 26:62,63 & Mark 14:60,61]. Further, to respond to their false accusations would have accorded credibility to their injustice. There would have been an exchange of words. Since there was none, the silence of Jesus condemned the process and thus fulfilled the prophecy about Himself: "He was oppressed, and He was afflicted, yet He opened not His mouth: He was brought as a lamb to the slaughter, and as a sheep before her shearers is dumb, so He openeth not His mouth" [Isaiah 53:7].

Communicating in silence before Pilate and Herod Antipas was tricky, but not for Jesus. The two powerful men had the ability and opportunity to declare Jesus guiltless. But the issues at stake were bigger than just words: politics, obedience to the Romans or to God, the will of God or that of men and prophecy. Hence, the two men needed to have their consciences placed on inquiry. They needed a personal deep search of their own souls. Pilate and Herod were vast in the legal processes of their people. However, they were babies in moral issues. They were not morally independent, though they had positions of authority. They asked questions without getting any answers [John 19:9 & Luke 23:9]. They had to confront themselves with divine justice. In Jesus' silence, they could not explain what they experienced. They lost authority in their own offices and could not make any rational decision. They outsourced their decisions to others: Herod to Pilate and Pilate to the multitude.

Biblically, adultery is a male and female sin. The Scribes and Pharisees knew this. To present a woman on account of sin of adultery [John 8:3,4], with the claim that she was caught in the very act, meant that they saw and knew the man who slept with the woman. However, they had brought her alone to Jesus to place Him in contention with the law and the word of God. Moses was the law and Jesus was the theology [John 8:5]. Depending on the responses of Jesus, the woman could be killed by stoning, the law of God may be put in derision and in contention with the law of Moses, and the authority of Jesus would be in doubt. The silence response of Jesus shifted the cynosure, from the woman to the questionable integrity and conscience of those who had brought

the woman. According to Ibrahim et al. (2023), the meaning of Jesus silence was transmitting a message to the accusers of the woman, and He was conversing with them in silence. He was asking questions to their consciences without saying a word. In silently writing on the ground, Jesus was asking the crowd questions that they could not answer in public, but in secret (Dinkler, 2012). Jesus used silence to enquire fair consideration of an issue or a question. He also used silence to reset the thought process of the human mind, which may divert understanding, when the verbal communication climate was at odd (Dhaqane, 2024).

The cross of Calvary is the loudest silent communication of Jesus. If it concerned the salvation of humanity, Jesus never presented any argument in defense of Himself, He considered the good of others (Lamijan et al., 2025). His silence was a symbol of His refusal to use His divine power to save Himself from pain and death. Stated below are specific silent communication examples, while Jesus hung on the cross. The examples are accentuated by the fact that at each point on the cross, Jesus had the power to step down from the cross and rise to heaven. Instead, He chose silence, suffering and restraint:

“... If thou be the Son of God, come down from the cross.” [Matthew 27:40c].

“... If He be the king of Israel, let Him come down from the cross, and we will believe Him.” [Matthew 27: 42b & Mark 15:32].

“And saying, if thou be the king of the Jews, save thyself.” [Luke 23:37].

“And one of the malefactors which were hanged railed on Him, saying, if thou be the Christ, save thyself and us.” [Luke 23:39].

The silence of Jesus to the temptation of performing a miracle to save and rescue Himself from His murderers was a judgment against them. He did not have to break the silence to perform such a miracle for Himself and commend curiosity in favor of injustice. Even under horrific situations, truth must be preserved and honored and human dignity and resilience encouraged (Okai et al., 2025). The context of this study disagrees with that of Utulu and Bello (2023). They found that silence can lead to speculation, increase conspiracy theories, and misjudge motives. This may be true in secular contexts. However, it was not true with Christ on the cross and the woman caught in adultery. In support, Makkar (2024) found that silence gave room for emotional reflection and that presence is appreciated more than words, which conveyed deep empathy (Gaitho, 2022).

Principles Of Servant Leadership

In most of the modern leadership thoughts and literature, leadership is domination. In Mark 10:43,44, Jesus countered that definition and expression by describing leadership as servanthood, to establish the effectiveness of leadership (Alharbi & Kundi, 2023). Theologically, anyone who is elected to be a leader has covenanted to be a servant to the people, not in words, but in deeds and actions. This process progresses from service to greatness and from slavery to being the first. In this sense, leadership is not control, power, or position. Instead, it is the process of services from the leader to the followers, according to Shao et al. (2022), to strengthen them and make them well-fit for the work, and according to Solomon and Emmanuel (2025), to perform better and increase productivity. Consequently, the servant leader guides the followers from taking to giving, from telling to asking, from forcing to choosing, from selfishness to selflessness, from

exploitation to sacrifice and from top-down to bottom-top decision-making process (Noland & Richards, 2015). This encourages the engagement of the followers (Harju et al., 2018).

While on earth, Jesus was a Supreme and divine leader. He not only deserved service and honor, but worship also. Nevertheless, He who angels worship, introduced Himself as: “The Son of Man did not come to be served, but to serve, and to give His life as a ransom for many.” [Mark 10:45]. As a Servant Leader, the Bible indicates typical indicators of servanthood from the life of Jesus.

Table I: Servant Leadership indices

1	2	4
INDEX	BIBLE TEXT	SERVANT LEADERSHIP FUNCTION
Sacrificial love	John 15:13	Authority + Love = Service Or Service = f (Authority, Love)
Humility and obedience	Philippians 2:6-8	Humility + Obedience = Self-Sacrifice Or Self-Sacrifice = f (Humility, Obedience)
Compassion	Matthew 9:36	Compassion + Empathy = Active support Or Active support = f (Compassion, Empathy)
Faithfulness	Luke 22:42	Self-surrender + Subordinated will = Redemptive outcome Or Redemptive outcome = f (Self-surrender, Subordinated will)

Authentic servant leadership is an outcome of authority and love, which leads to true service of the servant leader to the followers. Authority places the leader in the capacity to support, help and grow the subordinates. Misplaced Authority alone will dominate, harass, and intimidate [1 Peter 5:3; 1 Corinthians 13:1-3]. From Bible doctrine, authority legitimizes service and gives scope to it. This is because according to Matthew 28:18, authority is the power to serve. Love is the motivation of authority and gives it direction towards service to others and not over them nor against them [John 15:13]. Consequently, proportionate increases in authority and love will have a direct effect on service. Even in silence, the needs of people can be served (Anjum et al., 2025). In their findings, Jonker and Dube (2025) asserted that servant leadership results in supported service and stronger commitment from the followers.

Humility and obedience are twin principles that will directly lead to self-sacrifice. Humility is not self-reduction. As a human being, humility is the act of placing oneself in the right position before God and others. Humility does not consider position, education, power, wealth, and fame [Philippians 2:6-8]. Obedience subordinates the human will to the will of God. Humility is passive, but obedience actively raises humility on the scaffold. This combination produces self-sacrifice because self is diminished in humility and personal will is subjected to obedience to the higher authority. The outcome of self-sacrifice is extremely critical on the integration of humility and obedience. If one is missing in the process, the servant leadership becomes spurious.

In servant leadership, support is activated when the needs of others are appreciated (Abdou, 2025), and motivation is put into action to help, improve or change the situation [Romans 12:15]. Empathy is the feeling stage; compassion is the action stage. When one understands and becomes aware of the needs of others (Gaitho, 2022), the appropriate intervention follows [Matthew 9:36, 37; Mark 1:41]. This function renders the servant leader as a person who is other people-oriented (Lamijan et al., 2025). He or she responds to problems of followers and creates an atmosphere of citizenship attitude in the organization, in which the followers are well developed (Lumpkin & Achen, 2018).

The servant leader surrenders self, interest, and ambition to God and for the service of the followers. A leader who has surrendered self will be willing and ready to suffer and bear much pain if the will of God is served (Gaitho, 2022). Meanwhile, self cannot be surrendered without the human will being subordinated to the will of God. Subordinate is when a Servant leader resolutely allows the will and word of God to moderate his or her actions. With the combination of these two factors, the purpose of God is attained. The implication is that the mission of God is achieved by all involved.

Secular Case Studies of Eloquent Silence

There are examples in our current world of people who suffered innocently but responded in silence to the unjust situation they struggled with. They did not enjoy the experience but used silence to communicate their innocence and to condemn the unjust treatment. These people testified against the treatments and resisted them. Socrates was condemned unjustly in Athens. He used silence to communicate his innocence and supported truth rather than promote injustice (Udeze et al., 2013). When the officials asked him to break his silence and be released from the case, Socrates refused and affirmed that it is better to affirm truth than to survive. Further, the silent response of Socrates showed that the human conscience was more powerful than official power.

The Holocaust victims adopted silence to secure and preserve human dignity (Udeze et al., 2013). They faced horrendous situations like genocide, maltreatment, and humiliation. In such situations, words were encouraging to the perpetrators of such wickedness; as a result, they used silence as a form of resistance to barbarism. The silence became a loud herald of such barbarity, its condemnation, and a testimony against it. Mahatma Gandhi suffered from oppression of colonial domination and incarceration. He used the discipline of silence to demobilize the oppressors (Udeze et al., 2013). Gandhi learnt the principles of *Mauna*, which is the practice of silence in situations of crisis. Particularly political ones. He learnt how to understand a clearer picture of crises Ardana and Surya (2019), so as not to be reactionary, directed towards moral solutions and encouraged nonviolent resistance (Chakraborty, 2021).

During the 27-year imprisonment of Nelson Mandela, he used silence to condemn his persecutors and deny the psychological pleasure of seeing him in lament and complaints (Udeze et al., 2013). In his case, he used silence in a very strategic way. He refused to relate his issue to the prison wardens. While he did not want to dignify them with such knowledge, he understood that it did not serve any critical purpose to him. As a result, Mandela developed an air of authority and dignity around him (Berry, 2011). He became morally independent and was recognized as a disciplined prisoner, not a suffering one.

Discussion: Jesus, Eloquent Silence, And Servant Leadership

As a Servant leader, Jesus used silence to communicate deliberate theological information, which otherwise, would cause unnecessary wranglings and hence, distort truth. Arguments and speeches, expressions and verbalization can survive on charm and charisma, but they will leave the lowly servant leader without any such contributions. Jesus, the chief servant leader, provides a counter-cultural communication in silence, which does not support charismatic verbalism, but frowns at it with resolute silence in expectation of deliberate introspection and change (Berry, 2011). What this means is that Jesus does not always have to explain everything or defend Himself to avoid shame, pain, suffering, or even death.

In applying the principles of servant Leadership, Jesus did not apply His moral capital to affirm curiosity, theatricals, spectacles, and wonder-mongers. His silent communication was directed at reasonable reflection and deliberate decision to keep the word of God (Su et al., 2020). This way, evil decisions may be reversed, and innocent victims may be delivered. Hence, the rationale for the adoption of silence by Jesus was to develop character and engender spiritual growth. Baltezarević et al. (2022) disagreed with this reasoning. They argued that silence can reduce the tension of communication, but that it cannot increase creativity. Jesus applies servant leadership by silently, but faithfully, living under restraint, amidst excruciating conditions. This approach made people reflect on their course of action and change them (Celli & Willard, 2025), because of silence which was what they required as an appropriate form of communication. Edmondson and Besieux (2021), advanced that silence gave people the opportunity to think, to then speak and possibly act.

Recommendations

To many leaders and followers, silence under any form of wrong is lame, weakness, and acceptance of the action. This is the position of those who believe in expressions, assertiveness, visibility, and verbal defense. In many cases, these methods may often be used to intimidate, subdue initiatives, and destroy moral independence. The truth is that, used wisely, silence can communicate resistance against injustice, oppression, and suffering. Anyone who suffers hypocrisy, manipulation, and injustice can adopt silence as a method to communicate that these inconsistencies are not acceptable and that he or she cannot legitimize them by verbal responses. Aside from Servant Leadership, in other kinds of styles, the leader has the last say. Even when character and competence are at stake. In many cases, they are astride the organization like a colossus, while the followers work under their shadows. Such leaders dominate, overrule, manipulate, and even threaten subordinates. Servant Leadership operates in a platform where the leader serves the followers, not a type of servitude, but in the exercise of humility and obedience to the will of God. Other leadership styles may imbibe this service-oriented leadership process. It will lead to an outcome of citizenship atmosphere in the organization, in which the leader and the lead pursue the same purpose.

The indices such as sacrificial love, Humility, obedience, compassion, and faithfulness, imply that functional relationships exist that underpin the theological principles of servant leadership. Consequently, further research needs to be carried out into the following functions:

1. Service = f (Authority, Love)
2. Self-Sacrifice = f (Humility, Obedience)
3. Active support = f (Compassion, Empathy) and
4. Redemptive outcome = f (Self-surrender, Subordinated will)

Conclusion

Jesus did not use silent communication loosely and carelessly. For Him, silence was not ignorance, weakness, nor a reproach to the audience. When He did not respond to questions or to situations, Jesus was intentional and doctrinal. When thoroughly thought through, His silence was authoritative, wise and a typical application of servant leadership. He deliberately refused to stand up for Himself, respond to hypocritical questions nor argue over human duplicities. As a means, silence had the end of providing the platform for people to reveal their original intention, establish justice, truth and encourage intuitive reflections.

Silence is eloquent because it stands out and is different from the popular noise of words and expressions. Theologically, silence gives God the chance to speak and act to uphold His righteousness. For the silent one, it is evidence of discernment, forbearance, reverence, faith, lived eschatology, and submission to the divine will. Further, Silence does not fight; however, it is not empty but rather places absolute trust in God for ultimate judgement and vindication.

Within the context of Servant Leadership, silence is ethical and dichotomous to every other style. This is because, rather than dominating, the Servant leader is restrained and instead of self-assertion, there is humility and an intentional focus on goals and objectives based on selflessness. The silent communication of Jesus, like in the example of the woman caught in adultery, makes the weak to become independent and able to place their personal defense under the protection of God and His redemption. Thus, at Calvary, the silence of Jesus provide protection for truth, service to humanity and dignifying the human choice. This implication means that silent communication is not irresponsible. Instead, when applied as a subset of servant leadership, silence becomes an extraordinarily strong principle of leadership, with restraint, discipline, and moral resistance.

In all, we live in a world of expressions, noise, and survival of the fittest. The eloquent silence of Jesus is a counter-cultural challenge to the current leadership competition. This context will provide a platform for leadership to be for service to others. This will drive integrity, justice, empathy, faith, and the outworking of the will of God as organizational values.

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